

A Study On Artificial Intelligence Approaches in Big Data Database Management System

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the latest trend in the field of technology, but ways to tap its full potential in business and commerce are still evolving. AI's will have a vital role to transform database management systems across business whether on cloud or on-premises. Researchers are in the ongoing effort to take Big Data to the next level by integrating it well with AI, which is expected to make an incredible difference in people's lives. A database is basically a data pool that stores data in both sequential and non-sequential format. The integration of AI and Database Management System (DBMS) technologies plays a significant role in shaping the future of computing. AI in database management deploys machine learning models for data mapping and classification for faster processing and better analytics. AI helps the database management mainly in the field of data aggregation and organizing database storage. Database management is expected to fit in well with all emerging and future technologies to work collaboratively and change the destiny of any business by leading them in a meaningful way of developing. We report in this paper about several general approaches to AI/Big Data Database integration and various developments in the field of intelligent databases.

Keywords: Database Management System (DBMS), Data mapping, Data aggregation, Dataset, Data exploration.

1. INTRODUCTION :

With the rapid innovations of digital technologies, the volume of digital data is growing fast. Consequently, large quantities of data are created from lots of sources such as social networks, smartphones, sensors, etc. Such huge amounts of data that conventional relational databases and analytical techniques are unable to store and process is called Big Data. Development of novel tools and analytical techniques are therefore required to discover patterns from large datasets.

Big Data is produced quickly from numerous sources in multiple formats. Henceforth, the novel analytical tools should be able to detect correlations between rapidly changing data to better exploit them.

Traditional processing techniques have problems coping with a huge amount of data. It's necessary to develop effective ways for data analysis in big data problems. Various big data frameworks such as Hadoop and Spark have allowed a lot of data to be distributed and analysed. Furthermore, different types of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, such as Machine Learning (ML) and search-based methods were introduced to deliver faster and more precise results for large data analytics. The combination of Big Data tools and AI techniques has created new opportunities in Big Data analysis.

Big Data and AI have a synergistic relationship. AI requires a massive scale of data to learn and improve decision-making processes and Big Data analytics leverages AI for better data analysis. With this convergence, you can more easily leverage advanced analytics capabilities like augmented or predictive analytics and more efficiently surface actionable insights from your vast stores of data. With big data AI powered analytics, you can empower your users with the intuitive tools and robust technologies they need to extract high-value insights from data, fostering data literacy across your organization while reaping the benefits of becoming a truly data-driven organization.

However, when Big Data meets AI, the two complement each other, helping us analyse and implement large data sets in unique and unexplored ways. Both Big Data and AI are path breaking technologies in their own way as shown in Fig 1.

Fig. 1: AI with Big Data

AI is the simulation of human intelligence by computers. By applying machine learning algorithms, we can make ‘intelligent’ machines, which can employ cognitive reasoning to make decisions based on the data fed to them. Big Data, on the other hand, is a blanket term for Exponential computing power and techniques applied to large sets of data to mine information from them. Big Data technology also includes large scale memory devices, Open-source programming platforms, Machine Learning algorithms and then analysing data to make strategic decisions and improve business outcomes. Most companies deploy Big Data and AI in silos to structure their existing data sets and to develop machines which can think for themselves. So, when Big Data meets AI, they have the potential to transform both, the way data is structured and the way machines learn.

2. RELATED WORKS :

In this part, some preliminaries and related works for Big Data analytics are illustrated.

2.1 Big Data Definition and Characteristics:

Huge volumes of data gathered from various sources like sensors, transactional applications, and social media in heterogeneous formats. There are various definitions presented for Big Data. Generally, the term Big Data refers to a growing set of data that contain varied formats: structured, unstructured, and semi-structured data. Existing Database Management Systems (DBMSs) are not able to process such a huge volume of heterogeneous data. Therefore, powerful technologies and advanced algorithms are needed for processing Big Data.

The Big Data can be described using different V’s such as Volume, Velocity, Variety, Veracity and Value as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Big Data’s Characteristics

- **Volume:** This implies the huge quantities of data produced every second. These huge volumes of data can be processed in big data frameworks.
- **Velocity:** This denotes the speed of data production and processing to extract valuable insights.
- **Variety:** This specifies the various formats of data such as documents, videos, and logs.
- **Veracity:** This indicates the data quality factors. That is, it specifies the biases, noise, abnormality etc. in the data.
- **Value:** the most important “V” from the perspective of the business, the value of big data usually comes from insight discovery and pattern recognition that lead to more effective operations, stronger customer relationships and other clear and quantifiable business benefits.

Nowadays, more V’s and other characteristics such as Visualization and Volatility have been used to better define Big Data.

Management of Big Data is essential to efficiently manage data for creating quality data analytics. It includes efficient data collection from different sources, efficient storage using various mechanisms and tools, data cleansing to eliminate the errors and transform the data into a uniform format, and data encoding for security and privacy. The goal of this process is to ensure the availability, management, efficient and secure storage of reliable data.

2.2 Big Data Analytics:

Organizations can extract valuable information and patterns that may affect business through Big Data analytics. Thus, advanced data analysis is needed to identify the relations between features and forecast future observations.

Big Data analytics refers to techniques applied to achieve insights from huge datasets. The Big Data analytics results can improve decision-making and increase organizational efficiency.

Fig 3: shows various analytical approaches that are developed to extract knowledge from the data, such as:

- **Descriptive analytics** is concerned with analysing historical data of a business to describe what occurred in the past.
- **Predictive analytics** is focused on a variety of statistical modelling and machine learning techniques to predict future possibilities.
- **Prescriptive analytics** include descriptive and predictive analytics to recommend the most suitable actions to enhance business practices.

Fig. 3: Big Data Analytical Approaches

The Descriptive analytics, Predictive analytics and Prescriptive analytics are the three different analytics techniques used to make better and faster decisions on Big Data sets to uncover hidden patterns. Various researches address this field of study by improving the developed techniques, proposing novel methods, or investigating the combination of various algorithms. However, more analytical improvements are required to meet the challenges of Big Data.

2.3 Big Data Platforms:

Batch processing, Real-time processing, and Interactive analytics are different platforms of Big Data.

Batch processing platforms perform extensive computations and take time to process data. Apache Hadoop is the most common batch processing platform. It is used due to scalability,

cost-effectiveness, flexibility, and fault tolerance in big data processing. Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS), Yet Another Resource Negotiator (YARN), and MapReduce distributed programming model are some different modules of the Hadoop platform which operate across the big data value chain; from aggregation, storage, process, and management.

As defined, velocity is another characteristic of Big Data. It is defined as a continuous, and high-speed data stream that arrives at rapid rates, and requires continuous processing and analysis. Real-time processing platforms are used for fast and efficient analysis of continuous data streams. Apache Spark and Storm are two common examples of stream processing platforms. Stream processing would be required for various applications such as weather and transport systems.

Interactive analytics platforms enable users to access dataset remotely and perform various operations as needed. Users can connect to a system directly and interact with data. Apache Drill is an example of interactive analytic platforms.

3. OBJECTIVES :

Big Data and artificial intelligence are also linked in terms of research and technological innovation for each field. Big Data technology uses AI theories and methods and AI relies on large volumes of data and the supporting Big Data technologies to improve and evolve decision making capabilities.

- Towards sustainable development goals;
- As responses to social problems and challenges;
- For innovations in business, research, academia industry, and technology
- For theoretical foundations and contributions to the body of knowledge of AI and Big Data research.

4. STUDY OF EXISTING SYSTEM :

The surveys are classified into four main categories: Big Data Management Process, Big Data Analytics Techniques, Big Data Platforms and Big Data Analytics Applications.

4.1 Big Data Management Process:

The authors Tsai et al.[1] reviewed various studies related to traditional and recent Big Data Analysis. The procedure of Knowledge Discovery in Data mining (KDD) involving input, analysis, and output is

considered as the basis for these studies. Various data and Big Data Mining Techniques such as clustering and classification are there in the analysis step. Moreover, some open issues and future research directions have been suggested to provide efficient methods. However, their survey has not been written in a systematic way, the studies are not compared completely and the recently published articles are not included. Also, they have only focused on the Machine Learning category of Artificial Intelligence techniques, and other AI categories such as computational intelligence have not been studied.

Siddiq et al.[2] a detailed taxonomy was presented based on storage, pre-processing, processing, and security. Various articles have been discussed in each category. Furthermore, the features of the proposed methods were described in this paper, and different techniques were compared. Moreover, future works and open challenges have been discussed.

4.2 Big Data Analytics Techniques:

Athmaja, Hanumanthappa & Kavitha.[3] presented a systematic literature-based review of Big Data analytics according to the ML mechanisms. However, no categorization is provided for reviewing related studies in the present paper. Moreover, the non-functional features of the studies have not been investigated. The authors do not provide any systematic procedure for gathering the related studies. They have reviewed the existing big social media analytics approaches in five classes; artificial neural networks, fuzzy systems, swarm intelligence, evolutionary computation, and deep learning. The authors assessed the reviewed techniques based on their quality metrics. However, there is no systematic procedure to select articles related to this field.

A complete study of Big Data analysis tools and techniques has been presented by Mittal & Sangwan.[4] and they focused on studying machine learning techniques for Big Data analysis. Therefore, three categories are considered for reviewing selected techniques, which include supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning. Nevertheless, there is no clear method for article selection and the studies have not been evaluated based on quality parameters.

Qiu et al.[5] presented a brief review of the ML techniques and some recent learning methods, such as representation learning, deep learning, distributed and parallel learning, transfer learning, active learning, and kernel-based learning are highlighted in this review article. However, they only focused on ML techniques and the study reviewed a few papers in each classification. Also, the article selection procedure is not included in this paper. Moreover, in this paper, no technical comparison has been made in relation to the proposed methods. Another work is reported by

Sivarajah et al.[6] for the Big Data analysis techniques, The authors categorized these techniques into three main groups, including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics. However, there are some gaps in analysing the qualitative parameters, and the study selection process.

4.3 Big Data Platforms:

Oussous et al.[7] investigated the impact of Big Data challenges, and numerous tools for its analysis. The tools used for big data processing are discussed in this article. Also, the challenges of big data analytics are divided into six general categories: Big Data Management, Big Data Cleansing, Big Data Collection, Imbalanced Big Data, Big Data Analytics, and Big Data Machine Learning. The investigated research efforts directed toward big data processing technologies. The authors discussed some associated challenges, such as data storage and analysis, knowledge discovery and computational complexities, scalability and data visualization, and information security. However, the article selection process is not referred to and the studies have not been evaluated based on quality parameters.

4.4 Big Data Analytics Applications:

Vaishya et al.[8] studied the main applications of AI for prevention and fighting against Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). The authors recognized seven applications of AI for the COVID-19 pandemic:

- (1) Detection of the disease,
- (2) Monitor patient treatment,
- (3) Contact tracing,
- (4) Predicting cases and deaths,
- (5) Drug production,
- (6) Reduction of workloads,
- (7) Disease prevention.

However, this paper fails to take into account the following:

- Few papers were investigated
- The study selection process is not stated
- The qualitative parameters were not provided.
- Detailed taxonomy was not presented based on AI techniques.

Finally, the applications of AI techniques and big data to manage and analyse the huge volume of data derived from the COVID-19 disease. Five categories are considered for reviewing selected big data techniques, which include prediction of COVID-19 outbreak, tracking the spread of the virus, diagnosis and treatment, and drug discovery. Due to the investigated studies, there are some weaknesses in the current big data analysis surveys as follows:

- Many articles did not assess the qualitative metrics for investigating the techniques.
- Some papers did not present any reasonable classification of data analytics techniques in the context of big data.
- Some papers did not follow the paper selection procedure.
- Many articles did not present entire categories of artificial intelligence techniques for reviewing big data analytics.

The reasons mentioned led us to have a study on AI approaches to big data analysis to overcome all of these gaps.

5. PROPOSED RESEARCH :

This section provides guidelines for performing a systematic analysis for studying the Big Data Analytics approaches. The systematic analysis procedure includes a clarification of finding the related studies in scientific databases. The following Research Questions (RQs) are defined and answered according to the objectives and scope of the present survey:

- RQ1: What is the taxonomy designed for big data analytics techniques?
- RQ2: Which AI techniques are applied to big data analytics?
- RQ3: What qualitative features are assessed in AI approaches?
- RQ4: What are the big data analytics open issues?

After defining the research questions, some criteria are applied to select the final studies. The article selection process is shown in Fig.. 4. In this systematic procedure, some popular databases such as ScienceDirect, Springer Link, IEEE Xplore, and ACM Digital Library are used.

Fig. 4: The Article Selection Process

The selection process is done in three stages.

- **Stage 1:** 4,291 and additional 10 papers were identified through our keyword search strategy.

- **Stage 2:** Duplicate records are removed and some criteria are considered for selecting high-quality studies. Titles, abstracts, and keywords were studied to select the articles for the next step. Henceforth, 468 articles remained for re-evaluation.
- **Stage 3:** A review of the text of the selected studies from the second stage was performed to confirm these studies. A total of 32 articles were identified in this step.

5.1 AI-Driven Big Data Analytics Mechanisms: Classification and review of the selected Big Data Analysis studies are performed based on the AI subfields used in Big Data Analytics.

Fig. 5 shows the taxonomy of the big data analytics techniques based on the AI subfields, and categorizes the articles investigated in this survey within those categories. The presented taxonomy has four main categories:

- (1) Machine learning
- (2) Knowledge-based and Reasoning methods
- (3) Decision-making algorithms and
- (4) Search methods and optimization theory.

Fig. 5: Schematic Diagram of Classification of AI

Furthermore, the four most significant qualitative parameters are defined to assess each big data analysis method and recognize its benefits and drawbacks as follows:

- **Scalability:** The mechanism’s ability to adapt to rapid changes without compromising the quality of the analysis.
- **Efficiency:** It denotes the ratio of the method to the overall time and cost needed.
- **Precision:** This is detected with various parameters like data errors, and the predictive ability of algorithms.
- **Privacy:** It defines the practices which safeguard that the data is only used for its intended purpose. The papers are reviewed and compared with mechanism goals in the last step.

5.2 Machine Learning Mechanisms:

Machine Learning Algorithms can be divided into two main classes: Supervised learning and Unsupervised learning.

Supervised learning needs a lot of manual effort to put the data in a proper format to learn algorithms whereas unsupervised learning algorithms can discover hidden patterns in huge amounts of unlabelled data. Unsupervised learning is used for input data without the corresponding output variable. Clustering is one of the major types of unsupervised algorithms.

The aim of a Supervised learning algorithm is to forecast the right label for newly presented input data using another dataset. In this learning method, a set of inputs and outputs is presented and the relation among them is found while training the system. The main objective of supervised learning is to model the dependency between the input features and the target prediction outputs.

5.3 Knowledge based and Reasoning Methods:

Knowledge and reasoning is one of the major fields of AI. A reasoning system can perform better than a human expert using its knowledge base within a specified domain. Three selected knowledge based mechanisms are Belief Rule Base Systems, Rule-based Reasoning and Gamification Rules.

Recently, various classifiers have been developed to classify Big Data. Extended Belief Rule Base (EBRB) systems have shown their capability for Big Data and multiclass issues. However, time complexity and computing efficiency are two key challenges of BRB methods. Although, the development of context-aware applications for reasoning on resource-bounded mobile devices is challenging. Rakib & Uddin.[9] presented a context-aware framework with a lightweight rule engine and a wide range of user preferences to decrease the number of rules while inferring personalized contexts. The authors confirmed that associated rules can be reduced in order to enhance the inference engine efficiency in terms of accuracy, execution speed, total execution time, and execution cost. A solution to increase employee's motivation and encourage them to be more active has been proposed but it is performed by automatically detecting stressful situations and offering recommendations when identifying a stressful pattern. Two notions of workplace well-being are aggregated with gamification methods to analyse how it can aid employees to obtain the soft and hard skills to enhance their curriculum.

Recently, context-aware computing has received increasing attention in the IoT and pervasive computing. Context acquisition, context modeling, and context-aware reasoning are three major steps of

this method. Although, the development of context-aware applications for reasoning on resource-bounded mobile devices is challenging. Rakib & Uddin.[9] presented a context-aware framework with a lightweight rule engine and a wide range of user preferences to decrease the number of rules while inferring personalized contexts. The authors confirmed that associated rules can be reduced in order to enhance the inference engine efficiency in terms of accuracy, execution speed, total execution time, and execution cost.

Araújo & Pestana.[10] proposed a novel solution to increase employee's motivation and encouraging them to be more active. It is performed by automatically detecting stressful situations and offering recommendations when identifying a stressful pattern. Two notions of workplace well-being (i.e., physical and social) are aggregated with gamification methods to analyze how it can aid employees to obtain the soft and hard skills to enhance their curriculum.

Generally, the primary drawbacks of knowledge-based and reasoning mechanisms are the problems encountered during knowledge acquisition, as well as adaptability. Besides, these methods cannot be used for large quantities of data.

5.4 Decision Making Algorithms:

The aim of decision algorithms is to maximize the expected utility. In these algorithms, the desirability of a state is calculated using a utility function. The agent decides with the aim of maximizing the utility function.

Big Data Analytics applications need to be re-deployed when changes occur in the cloud at runtime. A decision-making solution for selecting the most appropriate deployment for big data analytics applications has been presented by Lu et al.[11]. First, a new language called DepPolicy is presented to specify runtime deployment information as policies. Then, MiniZinc is developed to model the deployment decision problem as a constraint programming model. Then, a decision-making algorithm is introduced to make various deployment decisions based on total utility maximization while satisfying all given constraints. Finally, a decision making middleware, called DepWare, is applied to deploy the application in the Cloud. The obtained result confirmed the functional correctness, performance and scalability of the proposed method.

5.5 Search Methods and Optimization Theory:

The Search Methods can be used to find the ideal solutions for a problem. In search-based optimization, ideal decisions are made based on some objectives within the given constraints. The search space in a big data environment becomes

larger. Therefore, powerful search algorithms need to be developed for large-scale optimization problems

6. RESULTS AND COMPARISON :

As mentioned in the previous sections, Machine Learning, Knowledge-based and Reasoning Methods, Decision-making Algorithms and Search-methods and Optimization Theory are the four main categories of Big Data analytics techniques.

The main achievements of these techniques are

- AI drives down the time taken to perform big data analytics
- Repetitive tasks can be done with the help of machine intelligence and
- Reduction of the error and enhancing the degree of precision.

As shown in Fig. 6, the popular technique that researchers use to analyse Big Data is supervised learning with 59%. Relevant techniques include regression, ensemble classifier, naive bayes, decision tree, random forest, support vector machine neural network.

Fig 6: Various AI Techniques

7. OPEN ISSUES AND CHALLENGES :

Some challenges for Big Data Analytics using AI techniques from various perspectives are:

- Fog computing
- Processing huge quantities of data
- Security
- Qualitative parameters and metrics
- Data quality.

8. CONCLUSION :

The state-of-the-art mechanisms in the field of Big Data Analytics are surveyed in this article. According to the performed study, we introduced a taxonomy for AI-driven big data analytics mechanisms. The selected 32 articles are investigated in four main categories including Machine Learning, Knowledge

based and Reasoning Methods, Decision-making Algorithms, and Search Methods and Optimization Theory. The advantages and disadvantages of each of these mechanisms have been investigated as below.

The Machine Learning-based Mechanisms use a learning method to adapt the automated decisions. Efficiency and precision are the major factors that are improved in most of the Machine Learning-based Mechanisms. However, the use of incomplete and inconsistent data may produce incorrect results.

The Search-based Optimization methods used various objective functions to find an optimal solution from a number of alternative solutions. These methods have high efficiency and high precision. Although, these methods are not scalable enough.

The Knowledge-based and Reasoning mechanisms improve the analytics quality using the knowledge base. The major advantage of Knowledge-based mechanisms is their relative simplicity of development. Although coverage for different scenarios is lower, whatever scenarios are covered by these mechanisms will provide high accuracy.

In Decision making algorithms, a decision making problem is modelled as a constraint programming problem and the desirable decision is made using a utility function maximization. These mechanisms have good performance in terms of scalability, efficiency, and precision.

The data gathered in this paper aid to explain the state-of-the-art in the field of Big Data analysis. This survey tries to perform a detailed systematic study but also has some limitations. It fails to study Big Data analysis techniques that are available in different sources. Furthermore, the articles which are not in the context of Big Data are not entirely investigated. Despite this, the results will help researchers to develop more effective Big Data Analysis Methods in Big Data environments.

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